

DETECTION OF DISLOCATIONS IN SHORT FIBRE REINFORCED MAGNESIUM ALLOYS BY NON-DESTRUCTIVE METHODS

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SUMMARY: Alumina short fibre preforms showing planar isotropic fibre distribution were infiltrated by commercially pure magnesium applying a direct squeeze cast process. Bending beams for internal friction measurements and rods for dilatometer and acoustic emission experiments were machined from the solution treated samples. During thermal cycling temperature, elongation and acoustic emission of the sample rods were recorded simultaneously. Thermal cycling causes internal stresses due to the difference in the coefficients of thermal expansion of the composite components. These stresses lead to permanent deformation of the specimen by creep and plastic flow. The total acoustic emission and the burst emission activity are correlated with plastic deformation mechanisms of the material. Damping and reversible stress relaxation experiments performed after thermal cycling show a strong dependence of the critical strain amplitude on the top cycle temperature and indicate an increase in the dislocation density with the top temperature.

KEYWORDS: acoustic emission, stress relaxation, damping, dilatation, thermal cycling, magnesium, alumina short fibre, thermal stresses

INTRODUCTION

During the last decade metal matrix composites (MMCs) based on magnesium have been developed and manufactured by various techniques to achieve low density composites with a high specific strength, stiffness and creep resistance even at elevated temperatures [1]. Additional advantages of Mg composites in comparison to unreinforced Mg alloys are e.g. improvements in the fatigue and wear resistance and a significant reduction of the thermal expansion. For economic reasons the development of Mg MMCs is focused on short fibre or particle reinforced MMCs rather than continuous fibre reinforced. A volume fraction of at least 15-20% reinforcement is preferential for an effective increase of strength and stiffness in particle or short fibre reinforced Mg MMCs [2,3]. For applications that require tensile creep strength a short fibre reinforcement of advanced creep resistant Mg alloys is recommended. Squeeze casting is considered as an economic method for producing short fibre reinforced Mg MMCs [2,4]. The load transfer from matrix to fibre is maintained by the interface that is strongly influenced by reaction products. Silica stabilised δ -Al₂O₃ fibres can be preheated in air up to temperatures higher than the liquidus temperature of Mg alloys without any damage and show almost no degradation during solidification of the Mg melt in the squeeze cast process or during subsequent heat treatment of the MMC [5]. For many Mg alloys reaction

product formation at the interface can be controlled by a proper heat treatment and therefore δ -Al₂O₃ short fibre reinforced Mg MMCs show a sufficient interface strength and a good thermal stability of the mechanical properties [6]. Mg melt infiltration of δ -Al₂O₃ short fibre preforms by squeeze casting is a promising way to improve the mechanical properties of Mg alloys at room and elevated temperatures beyond the limits of alloy development at a reasonable cost/benefit ratio.

Thermal stresses are generated in MMCs due to the difference in the coefficients of thermal expansion (Δ CTE) between the reinforcement and the matrix during the production process or any further temperature change. These thermal stresses can lead to the generation of new dislocations as it was proposed by Arsenault and Fisher [7] and shown by the etch-pit technique for Cu-W composites [8]. The dislocation generation owing to CTE mismatch is considered as one important strengthening mechanism [9]. Because of the induced thermal stresses thermal cycling is one of the most severe thermal environments and assumed to be more dangerous for MMCs than for monolithic alloys [10]. In-situ transmission electron microscopy observations have proven the increase in the dislocation density in Al-SiC composites during thermal cycling [11,12]. Large acoustic emission activity during the first three cooling intervals of thermally cycled SiC-particle reinforced Mg alloy QE22 was explained by the generation of fresh dislocations and displacement of the dislocations under the increasing thermal stresses during cooling [13]. The effect of thermal cycling on the microstructure, mechanical properties and stress state of MMCs is very well summarised in the standard text books on MMCs [10,14-16]. Such dimensional changes are a result of the thermal stresses introduced by thermal cycling and the relaxation mechanisms influenced by a lot of parameters (i.e. applied temperature-time profile, mechanical properties and their temperature dependencies, creep conditions, additional external load). The deformation of MMCs during thermal cycling holds the potential for a MMC forming process [17,18].

The effect of thermal cycling on the properties of squeeze cast δ -alumina short fibre reinforced Mg alloys has been investigated recently. Low load hardness measurements of δ -alumina short fibre reinforced magnesium alloy AZ91 after thermal cycling between 40°C and 300°C indicate a work hardening effect for the matrix [19]. Dilatometer investigations show that the dimensional stability during thermal cycling strongly depends on the top temperature of the thermal cycle (henceforth top cycle temperature - T_{top}), the thermal history of the specimens and the mechanical properties of the matrix alloy [20,21]. It has been shown that for higher top cycle temperatures compressive stresses along the main axis prevail during the thermal cycle and result in shortening of the specimens. Reversible stress relaxation measurements were carried out in order to investigate the thermal stability of thermally cycled AZ91 and QE22 MMCs and good correlation was found between precipitation effects and the stress relaxation [22,23]. For large numbers of cycles an interface damage was indicated by a sharp increase of the stress relaxation [23]. Damping measurements, that have been evaluated in the framework of the Granato-Lücke theory, have shown a strong dependence of the amplitude dependent damping on T_{top} but not on the number of cycles up to 100 cycles between RT and 300°C [24]. Internal friction values are strongly influenced by ageing [25,26].

Measurements of elongation, acoustic emission (AE) and internal friction are well suited non-destructive methods to investigate the dislocation generation in δ -Al₂O₃ short fibre reinforced Mg alloys during thermal cycling. In-situ measurements of acoustic emission and elongation in combination with internal friction measurements after thermal cycling will help to differentiate the matrix deformation mechanisms during thermal cycling.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The commercially pure magnesium (cp-Mg with Al and Si as main impurities) was reinforced with SiO₂ stabilised δ -Al₂O₃ short fibres (Saffil[®] from ICI) using squeeze casting [1,2,4]. The preforms consisting of the short fibres (mean diameter and length 3 μ m and 87 μ m, respectively, after squeeze casting) and a binder (containing Al₂O₃ and starch) were preheated to a temperature higher than the temperature of the magnesium melt (preform 1000°C, melt 800°C) and then inserted into a preheated die (290 to 360°C). The pressure for forcing the melt into the die with the preform was applied in two stages (50MPa for 30s and 130MPa for 90s). The second step closes pores and shrinkage cavities. The short time of contact between the liquid metal and the fibres leads to only slight reactions between the fibres and the matrix. Mg₂Si and Mg₁₇Al₁₂ are formed at the matrix-fibre interfaces due to reactions of the melt with the Saffil[®] fibres and/or the binder. Diffractometer phase analysis provided some evidence for the presence of MgO. The fibres do not act as centres for heterogeneous nucleation due to high temperature of the preform [2]. The materials prepared were exposed to a solution annealing 520°C/5.5h finished by hot water quenching.

Specimens for the damping and the reversible stress relaxation measurements were machined as bending beams (88mm long with thickness of 3mm) with the reinforcement plane parallel to the main specimen plane. The damping measurements were carried out in vacuum (about 50mPa). The specimens fixed at one end were excited into resonance (the frequency ranged from 150 to 160Hz) by a permanent magnet and the sinusoidal alternating current in the exciting coil. Damping was measured as the logarithmic decrement δ of the free decay of the vibrating beam. The signal amplitude is proportional to the strain amplitude ϵ . Experimental details are described by Buchhagen et al. [27]. The reversible stress relaxation measurements were performed with an electronic balance that enables a defined strain to be applied to the bending beam by lifting or lowering the balance arm. The time dependent change of the stress in the beam is proportional to the change of the weight read out by computer. A more detailed description of the experiment including some correcting and averaging mathematical operations is given in [28]. The bending beams were heated in a resistance furnace for 15mins at various top temperatures and quenched in water. The damping measurements were performed at RT and afterwards the reversible stress relaxation at 31°C.

Specimens for the measurements of dilatation were machined as rods (50mm long and 5mm in diameter) with the reinforcement plane parallel to the main specimen axis. The specimen and a quartz piece of the same dimensions as the specimen were mounted into the specimen holder of the dilatometer. The thermal expansion of both was transmitted by quartz rods to the inductive displacement transducers outside the radiant furnace used for controlled heating and the elongation of the quartz rods eliminated by the differential measurement. A spring applies a force of 2N on the quartz rods to ensure good contact between the quartz rods and the specimens. The temperature was determined by the means of a PtRh10-Pt thermocouple mounted near to the MMC sample. Cooling of the specimens was realised by compressed air. A sawtooth time-temperature profile was applied with 15min intervals for heating and cooling respectively (Fig. 1). One quartz rod was used as a waveguide and the AE transducer was mounted on its surface by silicon grease. The computer controlled DAKEL AE facility consisting of a DAKEL-LMS-16 AE analyser and a high sensitive LB10A PZT transducer (85dB ref. 1V/ms⁻¹) with a flat response over a frequency range from 100 to 500dB and with built-in preamplifier 30dB was used to detect AE. This system operated with a two-threshold levels detection recommended by an ASTM standard [29]. The AE signal was filtered, amplified and then evaluated independently at two different threshold levels to get two AE

counts, N_{C1} and N_{C2} . The difference between the threshold levels was set at 20dB (corresponding total gains 105dB, 85dB, respectively) to discriminate high amplitude AE. Thus, the count N_{C1} corresponds to the lower threshold level and involves all AE counts detected (total AE count) whereas the count N_{C2} involves AE counts with higher amplitude only (burst AE count). No acoustic emission was observed during a check test with an unreinforced specimen. At all tests, another AE LB10A transducer placed on a steel piece close to the dilatometer equipment and a second, identically set up channel unit were used to monitor external disturbances, as net shoots, electromagnetic noise, external vibrations etc. Only very few such signals have been detected by this channel. The signals detected correspondingly in the measuring channel, if any, have not been taken into account.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 9 shows the increase of AE counts with increasing fibre volume fraction V_f . Note also the increasing AE burst count indicating more frequent rapid release of large stress concentrations. Increasing matrix twinning as it was observed for thermally cycled cp-Mg in [6] may be proposed to explain this behaviour.

Fig. 9: Acoustic emission activity of thermally cycled δ - Al_2O_3 short fibre reinforced cp-Mg vs fibre volume fraction. AE counts were evaluated for the whole heating and cooling periods of the 2nd cycle between 35 and 300°C. The box on the right side shows the sawtooth profile of temperature and elongation

In the following the response of the δ - Al_2O_3 short fibre reinforced cp-Mg MMC on thermal cycling with step by step increased top cycle (20K/15min) temperature will be discussed. Thermal cycling with step by step increased T_{top} leads to increasing plastic deformation as shown in Fig. 4. Thus, a change in the structure and density of dislocations can be assumed and is reflected in the internal friction measurements (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3.). Fig. 2 shows the strain dependence of the logarithmic decrement δ measured at room temperature for cp-Mg composite thermally cycled with step by step increased T_{top} . It is seen that the strain dependencies of δ for all the top cycle temperatures investigated exhibit two regions. In the first region of lower strain amplitudes the logarithmic decrement is only weakly dependent on the maximum strain amplitude whereas in the second region of higher strains it depends

strongly on the strain amplitude. The critical strain at the transition from region one to two is shifted to lower values with increasing T_{top} . The value of the critical strain for Mg-26.2 vol.% Saffil[®] composites is higher than that for Mg-20vol.% Saffil[®] studied by Trojanová et al. [30]. The differences in the damping behaviour between specimens thermally cycled to various temperatures can be attributed to the interaction between dislocations and point defects including small clusters of foreign atoms and to changes in the dislocation density. The strong strain amplitude dependence of the logarithmic decrement (Fig. 2) suggests dislocations unpinning processes that can be explained using the Granato-Lücke theory [31]. According to this theory the dislocation segments are pinned by weak and strong pinning points and the strain amplitude dependent logarithmic decrement δ_H can be expressed by Eq. 1.

$$\delta_H = \frac{C_1}{\varepsilon} \exp(-C_2 \varepsilon) \quad \text{with} \quad C_1 = \frac{\rho L^3 F_B}{6 b l^2 M} \quad \text{and} \quad C_2 = \frac{F_B}{b l M} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the dislocation density, L and l is the mean distance between strong and weak pinning points, respectively, b is the magnitude of the Burgers vector of dislocation, F_B is the binding force between weak pinning points and a dislocation and M is the unrelaxed modulus. The values of C_1 and C_2 are presented in Tab. 1. The value of C_2 is decreasing with increasing T_{top} . The decrease in C_2 for the top temperatures below about 160°C is stronger than that above 160°C. The values of C_1 exhibit no monotonic variation with temperature.

Table 1: Amplitude independent damping δ_0 and the Granato-Lücke constants C_1 and C_2 calculated for the curves presented in Fig. 2.

$T_{top}/^\circ\text{C}$	20	60	100	120	160	200	240	280
$\delta_0 \cdot 10^3$	2.57	2.24	2.45	2.88	3.09	2.95	4.45	4.69
$C_1 \cdot 10^4$	3.98	1.57	1.73	3.25	1.26	1.96	1.43	1.62
$C_2 \cdot 10^3$	1.93	1.41	1.10	1.19	0.72	0.74	0.55	0.49

Fig. 2: Logarithmic decrement vs strain amplitude of thermally cycled $\delta\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ short fibre reinforced cp-Mg with step by step increased top cycle temperature (20K/15min). Damping measurements were performed at RT after thermal cycling up to T_{top} as noted at the curves.

The stress relaxation measurements for the monolithic cp-Mg and the composite show a monotonic increase of the reversible stress relaxation ($\Delta\sigma/\sigma = \Delta E/E = \text{modulus defect}$) with time indicating a dislocation mechanism. Fig. 3 shows the modulus defect after 3600s versus T_{top} for reinforced and unreinforced cp-Mg. The values of the modulus defect for the cp-Mg samples are much higher than those for alloys measured by Kiehn et al. [22] indicating the strong influence of foreign atoms in solid solution on the modulus defect. The curve for the monolithic cp-Mg in Fig. 3 may be explained by fluctuations in the concentration of foreign atoms in solid solution. The curve for the cp-Mg MMC is more even because of the strong influence of the dislocation generation due to ΔCTE . The decrease from 160°C with its minimum at 200°C may refer to changes in the deformation mechanism of the composite during thermal cycling as also indicated by the variation of N_{C2} with T_{top} .

Fig. 3: Reversible stress relaxation $\Delta E/E$ after 3600s of reinforced and unreinforced cp-Mg vs top cycle temperature of thermal cycling (one cycle each T_{top}). The modulus defect of the cycled specimens was measured directly after the damping experiments (Fig. 2). For comparison the burst count of the thermally cycled composite from Fig. 4 is presented.

The dimensional changes during thermal cycling and the acoustic emission activity are compared in Fig. 4. The total number of AE counts (N_{C1}) increases with increasing T_{top} as well as the residual elongation. For top cycle temperatures higher than 160°C a significant number of high amplitude AE counts (N_{C2}) is registered. This coincides with the change of the Granato-Lücke constant C_2 (Tab. 1) and the modulus defect of the composite (Fig. 3) with T_{top} at about 160-170°C and might be attributed to deformation by twinning. It is worthwhile to note that the count values measured during heating and cooling period of one cycle do not differ very much up to $T_{\text{top}} = 200^\circ\text{C}$. For higher temperatures the number of AE counts during cooling is higher. Diffusional deformation processes and dislocation annihilation may take

place in the high temperature stage of the heating interval while during the cooling interval dislocation glide may dominate.

The effect of thermal cycling with T_{top} varied from 200°C to 400°C (5 cycles at each temperature) on the dimensional stability and acoustic emission is shown in Fig. 5. A comparison with Fig. 4 shows that the AE activity may be dependent on the starting top cycle temperature or the crystallographic orientation of the grains in respect to the fibres which was not checked. The total number of the AE counts and even more the number of burst emissions are reduced by starting the experiment at $T_{top}=200^\circ\text{C}$. As mentioned above the AE effects are more pronounced for the cooling interval of a cycle at higher top cycle temperatures. The figure can be subdivided in three characteristic temperature regions. The first region up to $T_{top}=280^\circ\text{C}$ is characterised by a monotonic growth of the residual expansion and a slight increase of the AE activity. The residual expansion shows an intermediate behaviour up to $T_{top}=340^\circ\text{C}$. A shortening of the specimen in the first cycle of a temperature step is followed by specimen growth along the main specimen axis in the following cycles. In this second region the AE activity is increased about two orders of magnitude in comparison to the first region and remains approximately constant. Thermal cycling with $T_{top}\geq 340^\circ\text{C}$ results in shortening of the specimens due to dominating compressive internal stresses. This effect was also observed in reinforced Mg alloys. Specimens with the reinforcement plane perpendicular to the main specimen axis show the complementary behaviour: shortening in the first region and elongation in the third region [21]. The AE activity grows with ongoing shortening of the specimen. Almost no AE bursts have been observed during the whole experiment.

Fig. 4: Comparison of acoustic emission activity and dimensional changes vs top cycle temperature during thermal cycling. AE counts were evaluated for the whole heating and cooling periods of the cycles between 33°C and T_{top} .

The most important feature of thermal cycling is the generation of dislocations and the stress relaxation by dislocation motion. Their movement is determined by the required stress in dependence of the temperature, the distribution of pinning points (i.e. l and L), the internal

stresses and the crystallographic orientation of the grains in respect to the fibres. According to Arsenault and Shi [11] the dislocation density ρ may be calculated as

$$\rho = \frac{B\Delta CTE\Delta T V_f}{bt(1 - V_f)} \quad (2)$$

where B is a geometric constant (between 4 and 12 depending on the reinforcement shape), ΔT is the temperature difference of the cycle and t is the smallest dimension of the reinforcement. The analysis of the damping measurements (Tab. 1) shows that the dislocation density ρ and the distance between the weak pinning points l increases up to $T_{top}=280^\circ\text{C}$. This agrees well with damping measurements [24] with T_{top} varied between 100°C and 450°C that indicate a minimum value for the Granato-Lücke constant C_2 between $T_{top}=300^\circ\text{C}$ and 400°C . Electrical resistivity measurements revealed only slight changes in the distribution of foreign atoms during thermal cycling up to $T_{top}=300^\circ\text{C}$ [32]. The approximately constant concentration of weak pinning points and the increase in dislocation density leads to an increase in l which means that the dislocations can break away from pinning points under lower stresses and the critical strain decreases (Fig. 2). The yield stress of the matrix decreases with increasing temperature, too. The stress necessary for the dislocation breakaway decreases with increasing temperature and, hence, thermal cycling may make easy the breakaway of dislocations. Thus, the dislocations can move and internal plastic flow occurs accompanied by AE (Fig. 4 and 5).

Fig. 5: Comparison of acoustic emission activity and dimensional changes vs top cycle temperature during thermal cycling. AE counts were evaluated for the whole heating and cooling periods of the cycles between 37°C and T_{top} .

The increase of AE activity with the fibre volume fraction V_f (Fig. 1) can be explained as a result of the dislocation generation during thermal cycling (Eq. 2). The variation of AE total count with increasing T_{top} can be explained if we consider that the thermal stresses and the dislocation density grow with increasing T_{top} assuming that Eq. 2 is valid up to $T_{top}=300^\circ\text{C}$. To explain the thermal cycling behaviour between $T_{top}=280^\circ\text{C}$ and 340°C (Fig. 5) a dynamic equilibrium of dislocation generation and annihilation may be proposed, leading to a constant value of ρ and significant AE. The change in the sign of the internal stresses from tension to compression in the main specimen axis for $T_{top}\geq 340^\circ\text{C}$ (Fig. 5) as well as the increased top cycle temperatures itself may lead to accelerated dislocation annihilation resulting in a decrease of the dislocation density and thereby more effective AE generation at lower temperatures. Additionally the change in the stress state could make twinning more favourable.

CONCLUSIONS

The influence of thermal cycling on the microstructure, especially on the dislocation generation and movement, can be characterised by non-destructive methods such as measurements of the internal friction, acoustic emission activity and residual elongation. The AE activity is proportional to the fibre volume fraction. Up to $T_{top}=300^\circ\text{C}$ the damping increases with increasing T_{top} and the critical strain decreases. Thermal cycling experiments with step by step increased top cycle temperature reveal several threshold values where the dislocation related behaviour changes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft. The authors acknowledge also support of this work by the Grant Agency of the Czech Republic under grant 106/96/0208, the Grant Agency of the Academy of Sciences under grant A2041607 and the Grant Agency of the Charles University under grant GAUK147/96. The experiments were carried out at the Department of Materials Engineering and Technology of the Technical University of Clausthal. One of the authors (PL) is most grateful to Alexander von Humboldt Foundation for financial support during his stay in Clausthal.

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